

RABBIT MEAT PRODUCTION BY BREED

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Enter. In recent years, rabbit farming has become a developing field in animal husbandry. In practice, the breeding and productivity qualities of rabbits are evaluated during the inspection of rabbits. Inspection works in rabbit breeding are carried out from October 1 of this year to September 30 of the next year, that is, throughout the year. Inspection work is carried out by a specialist - zootechnical inspector who has special knowledge of the selection and breeding of breeding rabbits, the breeding and use of breeding breeds, and their offspring in rabbit breeding. In this, breeding male and female rabbits, their seeds and embryos, and breeding rabbits are inspected. Rabbit inspection research institutions, enterprises, and farms engaged in breeding work, selection centers, immunogenetic control laboratories, control testing stations, embryo transfer (transplantation) centers, and other legal and natural persons - breeder product owners held in their homes. According to the inspection results, the rabbits in the herd are divided into categories determined by the evaluation results.

Validation work is carried out separately for each breeding rabbit breed, sex, and breeding period.

Every year, the breeding subjects develop a plan for the inspection of breeding offspring of rabbits for the next year. In this case, an expert recruited from abroad will be introduced in advance with the plan for the inspection of breeding offspring (materials) of rabbits. Based on the appeal of the breeding subjects, the enterprises engaged in breeding work in the regional cattle breeding develop a plan for the implementation of the breeding product (material) audit, and a foreign specialist is involved.

Breeding subjects must have the necessary information to inspect breeding rabbits and their children, in particular, documents confirming the origin, productivity, and other qualities of breeding rabbits, as well as regularly study and analyze news in the field of breeding.

Inspection of rabbits is held in different seasons depending on the direction of the breed. In the winter season, the breeding season of rabbits is taken into account.

Before inspection, rabbits are put through a veterinary foam, and sick and weak animals are separated into a separate groups.

Based on the information from the inspection, it is selected for the seed core (plemyadro), and the seed core is filled with them. A mating plan is drawn up to effectively use the bred breed. Other plans are also made, such as the breeding of breeding rabbits and the sale of breeding rabbits from one farm to another. Indicators of all male and female rabbits in the main groups of the breeding farm are studied. Female rabbits and all young

rabbits in groups from which the main breed is obtained and rabbits sold to other farms are inspected in November-December.

All the male rabbits of Tovar and farmers, farms, and 3-month-old rabbits are selected for the main herd, and they are inspected in November-December to form a breeding nucleus.

The inspection event is mainly held with the participation of farmers and farm managers, farm zookeepers, and veterinary workers.

During the inspection of 3-month-old rabbits, which are removed to fill the herd, and 2-month-old rabbits, which are sold for breeding, their breed, live weight, body structure, color, wool layer thickness, and proportions are evaluated.

Live weight, body structure, color, the thickness of the wool layer, the color of the tivit in the 2-month-old breeding rabbits sold for the breeding of rabbits, the color of the tivit in the tivit (in the direction of the tivit), and the breed of rabbits in the meat direction (in the meat-skin direction), is evaluated based on live weight, body structure and evenness of wool layer.

The breed and breeding of rabbits is determined on the basis of relevant zootechnical documents.

Purebred rabbits are taken from the descendants of one breed (derived from the IV-generation), the rabbits of the acceptable type, which clearly show their belonging to this breed, obtained by the method of blood absorption.

Live weight - rabbits are given appropriate classes by measuring them to the nearest 100 g by weighing them individually.

Body structure - the exterior of rabbits is evaluated by looking at the lamb.

In this, the thickness of the bones, the width and depth of the chest, the size of the head, the straightness of the waist and the correct position of the legs are studied (Fig. 1).

1- picture. Rabbit body parts:

1 - head; 2 - neck; 3 - ear; 4 - the skin part of the neck; 5 - chest half; 6 - lateral head; 7 - waist; 8 - hump; 9 - tail; 10 - lower leg; 11 - number; 12 - back leg; 13 - tail; 14 - front leg; 15 - chest; 16 - nails; 17 - chest area.

Evaluation of the rabbit's exterior begins with the rabbit's head, then ends at the hind and front legs. In this, special attention is paid to the strong development of bones, the development of muscles, the thickness and sparseness of the fur. Also, in the assessment, special attention is paid to the dependence of the breed and breed of the rabbit on body parts and the differentiation of their reproductive organs.

The exterior indicators required in the evaluation are as follows; head-to-body ratio, male rabbits should have a larger, heavier, and rougher head than female rabbits. Ears should be straight and attached to the body, the hair should be dense (by the direction of the breed),

and the chest should be well-developed, wide, and deep. The waist should be short and straight, the loin-buttock part should be longer, wide, and full, the buttock should be round, and the legs should be developed and placed correctly about the body.

A drooping and widely located ear is considered a defective body structure, sometimes drooping ears in the rabbit breed are a (hereditary) sign of this breed.

Figure 2. Appearance of rabbit ears

1 - average; 2 - the ear is well placed; 3 - hanging ear

Summary. A very long neck also defines the weakness of the body. Short chest with underdeveloped chest, bent and drooping waist. The length of the neck also determines the weakness of the body. A short chest with an underdeveloped chest, a bent and drooping loin, a cut or drooping rump, too short or wrongly positioned in relation to the legs of the body are body defects.

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